

THE PATH OF PERSONAL GROWTH: VOICES OF ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM LEARNERS IN VALENCIA CITY

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ABSTRACT

Many choose to drop out of school for a variety of reasons. Regardless, few chose to continue after a break despite hindrances and the unfamiliarity of the new set-up, which led them to uncover new experiences in the path of Alternative Learning System (ALS) learning. The study focused on exploring the experiences of ALS learners in their learning journey. The participants were eight learners at the ALS Learning Center in Valencia City, Bukidnon, who were currently enrolled in the ALS program and at a secondary level. The researcher used narrative inquiry design in utilizing storytelling and re-storying, employing poetic interpretation of their journey as ALS learners. The data revealed the theme of personal growth among ALS learners. Their experiences contained both positive and negative notes; however, they are worth uncovering. The ALS learners, who are participants in this study, strived to finish the ALS program and participate in the ALS Accreditation and Equivalency Test (A&E Test). Their perspective was to complete their current level and align their age with the appropriate grade level. The interpretation showed that their experiences in ALS contributed to their personal growth, shaping their intellectual development, time management skills, and overall self-improvement.

Keywords: *ALS, Lived Experiences, Narrative Inquiry, Personal Growth*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, many choose to drop out of school. In the study of Atilano et al. (2016), a learner who is not interested in what is being taught in school and becomes lured out with earnings from a certain employment result in being dropped out. Despite progress in accessing the quality of basic formal education, 11 percent of youths stop school even prior to completing the final grade level (UNESCO Institute for Statistics [UIS], 2021). According to the Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA] (2017), 9 percent of people between the ages of 6 and 24 opted not to attend a regular school in 2017, and 83 percent of the people in this group were between the ages of 6 and 24. Unfortunately, many of the dropouts end up either unemployed or with menial jobs that pay low wages, which offers job instability.

A parallel education established by the Department of Education (also known as DepEd) within the provision of a Regulations for Primary Education, referred to as Republic Act 9155, entails the development of the ALS, or Alternative Learning System to offer young people who are not in school and adult illiterate with a complete fundamental education depending on their situation and needs. This program intends to become an alternative to current formal education instruction, utilizing informal sources of knowledge in a non-formal setting. It becomes a passage for school dropouts to develop self-drive in pursuing education despite the hindrances and attaining employment prospects.

In 2016, a prior change to the ALS program has been made to strengthen, intensify, and expand its implementation—the emergence of ALS Program 2 and the finalization of the ALS K-12 Basic Education Curriculum. Although they are not identical, the curriculum's learning strands are largely in line with the K–12 curricular for Basic Education in the official school system. According to the Department of Education (2017), the learning strands are as follows: Communication Skills (English, Filipino) [LS1], Scientific Literacy and Critical Thinking [LS2], Mathematical and Problem Solving Skills [LS3], Life and Career Skills [LS4], Understanding the Self and Society [LS5], Digital Citizenship [LS6] (Department of Education, 2017).

What keeps the learners motivated in undergoing the ALS is the vision that a certain opportunity will open upon finishing the program (Valeza et. al. 2017). In 2018, ALS had 840,521 participants (DepEd, 2018). In recent years, the ALS has made significant progress towards its objectives; however, it attracts only a fraction of the country's large out-of-school population, making it one of the challenges that the system faced.

In the theory of Ryff and Keyes (1995), personal growth is one of these characteristics that characterize psychological well-being, or optimal thriving. These characteristics include environmental mastery, autonomy, positive connections with others, self-acceptance, and a life purpose. Thus, personal growth is a result of life's experiences; for instance, the experience of poverty, family problems, or any personal problem, and how they manage and grow as individuals. As such, Geise (2008) defined

personal growth as the subjective perception of behaviors, thoughts, and feelings that are then interpreted as adaptive.

After the learners finish the ALS self-instructional learning modules in their Individual Learning Agreements (ILA's) with their constant consultation with their facilitators, they can take the A&E Test (Accreditation and Equivalency). If they pass, a government certificate will be given that is a substitute for a school diploma in the formal education system and will give them the chance to return to formal schooling (World Bank, 2018). Given these opportunities, it becomes essential to understand the experiences of ALS learners and how participation in the program contributes to their personal growth. Thus, this study sought to explore the lived experiences of learners in the Alternative Learning System.

Research Questions

The researcher looked into the lived experiences of learners in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in Valencia City, Bukidnon. It particularly aimed to respond to the question:

What experiences do learners in the Alternative Learning System have?

Review of Technical Literature

The narrative inquiry was first used by Connelly and Clandinin. In view of that, narrative is the study of experience taken from and from the actual stories. Clandinin and Connelly (2000) emphasized narrative inquiry, which highlighting storytelling as an effective means for reflection on the specific knowledge teachers has and how they communicate with that information. Connelly and Clandinin emphasize the significance of context and the interconnectedness of personal and cultural narratives in molding human lives and identities. As the author indicates, "Narrative inquiry provides an opportunity for personal and social growth for both the participants and the researcher as they each go through the reflective and generative process of constructing narrative experience as told, learned, and written" (Costantino, 2001, pp 108-109).

1. Basic Principle of Narrative Inquiry

In a study using narrative inquiry, the central principle is to look into and understand human experiences and views through storytelling and personal narratives. According to Chan (2017), analyzing narratives regarding to the practice environment led a new perceptive of teaching and learning and turns into an important tool for reflection. Researchers gather qualitative data, such as interviews or personal stories, to find themes, patterns, and perceptions associated with the research question. The emphasis is on the person's interpretation and organization of their experiences into complete stories, highlighting the function of narrative in constructing understanding, identity, and meaning. Hence, the narrative work's purpose is to present untold or undocumented stories that contradict existing or established narratives (Wolgemuth & Agosto, 2019).

2. Procedures for Conducting Narrative Research

These ways of conducting narrative research came from Creswell (2006) upon reviewing Clandinin and Connelly's (2000) general procedural guide.

2.1. Determine Research Problem or Question

Clearly state the research question or topic of interest that the narrative research will best meet. This method works best for apprehending the in-depth narratives or actual events of an individual or a select group of people (Creswell, 2006). This could be linked to understanding individuals' experiences, perspectives, or building identity over their narratives. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), research problems convey stories of individual experiences.

2.2. Select Participants

Select and classify participants who have stories that align with the research question. This may consist of purposive sampling to ensure that participants can provide rich and meaningful narratives with regard to the research topic. Locate one or a number of people that has lived experiences or memories to share and share quite a bit time with them to gather various types of information from their stories (Creswell and Poth, 2018).

2.3. Collect Narrative Data

To collect data, use qualitative methods such as interviews, storytelling, diaries, or personal narratives. Researchers can also gather the letters that the people have written, arranged stories about family members, collect documents (e.g memos or official emails) the people involved, or take photographs or a collection of objects that convey memories, and other social-familial-private artifacts ((Creswell & Poth, 2018). Thus, participants will have the chance to express their perspectives, events, and stories in the way they prefer.

2.4. Analyze Participants Story

Analyze the participants' narrative to identify themes, categories, or patterns, and rewrite it to organize it chronologically. The investigator could have actively participate and "restory" the narratives in an orderly structure. The method of rearranging the narratives into a general context is known as restorying (Poth and Creswell, 2018).

2.5. Collaborative Analysis and Reflection

Take part in collaborative analysis and reflection with participants or colleagues to validate interpretations, get deeper insights, and ensure rigor, validity, and reliability in the narrative inquiry process. According to Clandinin & Connelly (2000), narrative inquiry is a method of comprehending experience; it involves cooperation between participants and researchers over time, in a location or series of locations, and in social interactions with surroundings.

2.6. Present and Communicate Findings

Present the findings of the narrative study in a clear and captivating manner, using participants' narratives to put emphasis on key themes, insights, and interpretations. Look at how the results contribute to existing literature, theory, and understanding of narrative and human experiences.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a qualitative data approach, narrative inquiry with poetic interpretations. Clandinin & Connelly (2000) highlighted that narrative inquiry involves a method for comprehending reality that involves cooperation amongst individuals and researchers over an extended period in a location or set of areas, and in relations with surroundings. As Butina (2015) noted narrative inquiry is an aspect of qualitative inquiry where narratives serve as unprocessed information. In research, poetic interpretation (poetry) can be employed in data analysis and presentation of results as well as in the research process (Fitzpatrick & Fitzpatrick, 2020).

The study was conducted in an ALS Learning Center in Valencia City, Bukidnon, Philippines. The ALS schedule for attending school is Monday, Wednesday, Friday, and Saturday. The center, located in Valencia City Central, served as a key place to meet for learners who seek non-formal educational opportunities. These centers deliver information about the particular experiences that learners with ALS face. Eight participants were selected through the purposive sampling technique. The selection of participants must meet certain requirements. First, they were Valencia City-based learners. Second, they were currently enrolled in ALS programs. Third, they were at the secondary level of ALS. Last, they participate voluntarily. Table 1 presents the participants' profiles.

Table 1. Participants' Profile

Participants (Code Name)	Age	Religious Affiliation
Erin	16 years old.	Seventh Day Adventist
Tara	25 years old.	Roman Catholic
John	32 years old.	Roman Catholic
Tata	15 years old.	Roman Catholic
Nate	19 years old.	Roman Catholic
Shane	18 years old.	Iglesia sa Dios Espiritu Santo
Carlo	16 years old.	Iglesia sa Dios Espiritu Santo
Sitti	36 years old.	Islam

Rich and intricate narratives were collected from participants through in-depth interviews. The researcher used thematic analysis to pinpoint patterns, themes, and insights within the data of the narratives provided by participants. The analysis process generated familiarization, where the researcher immersed themselves in the narratives to gain a deep understanding of the participants' experiences and stories. Initial codes

were then produced to highlight key ideas, events, and emotions conveyed by the ALS learners. These codes were grouped into comprehensive themes and categories, capturing the commonalities and differences in the participants' experiences within the ALS program. Themes were polished and reviewed through an iterative procedure of data coding and interpretation, ensuring the accuracy and credibility of the findings. Thematic saturation was observed as the gathering of data increased to include narratives from additional participants, indicating an inclusive coverage of evolving themes. As stated by Naeem et al. (2024), saturate occurs when each data source underwent a comprehensive analysis and no fresh data or patterns are emerging from the data set. Member checking was conducted to validate the interpretations and make sure that the participants' voices were precisely represented. The findings of the data analysis provided a wide-ranging and nuanced understanding of the experiences of ALS learners in Valencia City, Bukidnon, stressing the transformative impact of the program to their personal growth. The researcher asked for ALS learners' informed consent before enabling them to take part in the study. Researcher safely stored and anonymized the data; one can preserve the participants' privacy and confidentiality. The researcher stands by the ethical standards that guarantee the rights and welfare of learners with ALS during the research process. A poetic representation of the themes and participants' verifications was achieved through interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study explored the lived experiences of learners in the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in Valencia City, Bukidnon, with a focus on how these experiences shaped their personal growth. The researcher heard the narrative stories of each participant and organized them into poetic interpretations.

The study was categorized into the theme Personal Growth, reflecting how ALS learners developed resilience, skills, and self-awareness through their educational journey. All the participants in this study affirmed that their experiences with ALS learning molded them into the people they are right now. These paths are worth uncovering and fighting for. This would shape them into a better version of themselves.

This is the story of Shane, who returned to ALS after two years of pause, determined to continue her education. She faced challenges in understanding lessons, managing time, and financial struggles, yet she remained focused on her goal of graduation. With guidance from her teachers and the skills she learned she adapted, persevered, and grew. Her journey reflects personal growth through persistence, discipline, and resilience.

*Two years paused, my schooling lost,
Voices of friends and neighbour's crossed
"You can finish, rise instead,"
Their stories guide me where I led.*

*Far from home, I step each day,
Lessons wait, I find my way.
Money short, and food runs thin,
Yet deep inside, I feel to begin.*

*Life and career skills, I slowly learn,
Budgeting, planning, a path to earn.
Computers, spreadsheets, I now explore,
Skills I lacked, I find once more.*

*Though tired and hungry, I don't let go,
I think of my purpose, and the growth I know.
Support and guidance light my way,
One step closer to graduation day.*

Personal Growth

Personal growth is fundamental for both individual and organizational performance (Woerkom & Meyers, 2019). According to the study by Lee et al. (2018), it is usually considered an outcome of intrapersonal processes where personal resources reside within the person. Participants state why they enrolled in ALS and how they fought with the hindrances they face. John states that he will finish his schooling; he will pursue education even without support. Nate added that his main focus is to learn; even if he only acquired a little knowledge, he would still work hard. Some participants said that the reason they continued their schooling was to help their family and siblings.

Some participants narrate the challenges they experienced before enrolling in the ALS program. And how they came up with a decision, which is to continue their studies. Nate narrated his experience before he decided to enroll in ALS. He said that “while I was in second grade, my parents separated. And we moved to Davao, so we had to transfer schools, but unfortunately, it did not happen. So, we decided to move back to Don Carlos, where I originally lived. Since we came back to Don Carlos, our lifestyle has not changed, and we are still poor. That’s when I decide to stop because of the hardship” (Broken family... kanang pagka Grade 2 palang grade 2 ko ato is ano... nang... kanang gai adto namig Davao tas mao to pag adto namu, ga itransfer me didto kay pa skwelahon lage daw unta me daw didto unya wala manpud na dayun mao to nibalik napud meg Don Carlos. Taga Don Carlos ko, nibalik dayun kog Don Carlos pobre napud kayo, mao nang lisod napud kayo mu skwela. Mao tong undang nalang kay nag decide ko mu undang kay lisod kayo). The reason Nate decided to stop is because of the separation of his parents. Lopez et al. (2018) concluded from their study that broken families impact negatively on children's safety, care, and discipline.

Shane described her technological experience in the ALS program; she said that “studying in ALS helped us a lot in making portfolios, and everything in computers I learned here” (Dako jud syag tabang maam, sa paghimo sa portfolio, sa mga computer wala jud koy hanaw ma’am. Diri naka toon jud ko). In the current knowledge-based

society, technological skills are already critical, and they seem to be important in the future for society as a whole in addition to basic capacities (Rodrigues et al., 2021). Shane added that “I learned to make a PowerPoint, spreadsheet, and Excel” (unsaon paggama sa mga PowerPoint, mga spreadsheet, sa Excel kanang mga ing.ana bitaw ma’am unsaon sya paggamit).

Some challenges that the participants faced were about handling their schedules while attending school, since some of them had to look for a job to survive. Shane said that “I used to do Bayong sidelines every Saturday, which is why we struggled to look for other sidelines. Because our vacant days were only Tuesday, Thursday, and Sunday, then our one vacant is Saturday, which we used to make Bayong” (Adtong niagi nag sideline jud ko aning bayong, every Saturday to sya mam, mao tong naglisod me ug sideline kay kuan raman Tuesday.. Thursday ug Sunday ragyud ang bakante namo kay Saturday diri bayong, lisod kaayo jud. Murag maka raos ragyud me). Time management skills are essential for academic success as well as, eventually, professional success (Adams & Blair, 2019). Nate mentioned that he can’t look for a job because he is not fit for a job because of his limited time.

Nate revealed that he only supports himself. He looked for a job and used his salary for his expenses, and sometimes he attended school with an empty stomach. Nate said that “I only support myself” (ako ra bayay naggasto sa akong kuan kaugalingon). And he added that “I looked for a job and used my money for expenses, and sometimes I don’t eat. Just like now, I don’t have breakfast. I walked here even with an empty stomach, as long as I could attend.” (murag nagkuan nalangko... sa tarbaho nalang naku gi akong ginakuan, akong ginakuan akong kwarta kay akong gina gasto diri ana bitaw....Mao rapud baya na, usahay dili naku ka... dili naku ka.... Karun wala gani koy pamahaw karon (smile) dali-dali, nagdali-dali gani kog kuan gani. Nag dali-dali kog lakaw diri bahala walay kaon basta maka anhi kay unsa na? talagsa ra kayo ko ka skwela). As Norazlan et al. (2020) state in their study that “financial problems are serious concerns that need attention since they can lead to a variety of other issues, including those related to health and academic performance.”

Participants shared how they overcome the challenges. Nate said that “I want to prove to them that I survived and that I can” (ginatagaan gyud naku ug kusog nga makaya gyud naku, nga gusto pud naku ug kanang ipa prove gyud sa ilaha nga kuan ba, kanang gikaya kay kaya gyud naku). According to the self-worth theory of Covington (1984), most people will do whatever it takes to “protect their sense of worth or self-value,” even if it means that achievements are going to happen. John said that “I think of the future; I know that having a diploma will help me find a good job” (kabalo baya ta nga taas ang standard diri sa Pilipinas, dili ka makakita ug saktong trabaho ug wala kay nahuman. Mao na mag human gyud kog skwela).

On the other hand, John stated how they helped each other: “I like to help, especially my classmates who are struggling” (Pareha baya me galisod mam, pero kaya raman. Gusto ko gatabang sa ila, labina kanang galisod bitaw sa mga lesson dayun mga advice pud). Also, Nate recounted his story of how his classmates and teacher

encouraged him to continue. “The ones that helped me were them (pointing at his classmates and teacher). There were times that I wanted to stop going to the ALS center because of problems. But they gave me strength to continue” (Oo naka tabang sa akua mga kuan gyud sila (pointing at his classmates and teacher). Murag nag kuan baya, murag naghuna-huna baya unta baya gyud ko ato nga mag undang nalang gyud ko diri ba. Maglisod mangyud ko, unya silay nagpakusog sa akua. Kanang ayawg kuan, aya gyud ug kuan. Talagsa ra baya gyud na pero padayon lang gyud, lingaw-lingawan nimo para makakuan ka ana.). The support that Nate received from his classmates and teacher helped him overcome the challenges he faced. Mtshweni (2024) emphasized that perceived social support from family, friends, and others plays a crucial role in helping students persist academically, particularly in flexible learning environments. ALS learners stated that their obstacles will not prevent them from accomplishing their goal. In addition, helping each other helped them overcome the challenges they faced.

Here’s the poetic interpretation of Nate's approach to acquiring personal growth as an ALS learner. Despite what life throws at her, she stands still and continues to grow.

*Life is about ups and down
A saying that I always hear around
Wondering if I am one to bound
And the one to be left on the ground*

*Difficulties emerged, give troubles in mind
Family problems, life is not so kind
What would I do, when I am bound to crash
That even I, feel like I’m a trash*

*Family's needs, obligations embraced
Education is nowhere to be traced
With heavy heart and sights profound
Accepting faith that’s what comes around*

*Wait, let us not forget the strength,
In battles we fought, despite the length.
Education’s flame it is still at heights
Someday we know we’ll reach the light*

*ALS program, give life’s a chance
In success we had a glance
Knowledge seeks knows no age
Letting myself grow with courage*

*I’ve been shaped by struggles
Let myself blooms from numerous stumbles
I am now firm and tight
Waiting for more challenge that will make me more bright*

Conclusions

The study focused only on the voices of ALS learners, highlighting their experiences. It clearly showed that they were shaped by these experiences throughout their journey. The participants, Erin, Tara, John, Tata, Nate, Shane, Carlo, and Sitti, narrate unique stories based on their journeys as ALS learners. Their story reminds us that the ALS program is a huge opportunity for out-of-school children. They were offered the chance to pursue their studies through another form of learning. This gave the participants hope and ease, assuring them that they were not deprived of their rights in education because they were supported by the program. The researcher also found that learners acquired skills in weaving Bayong, which provided them with extra income, and they learned technological skills that are relevant in today's generation. Some participants pointed out that weaving Bayong could be a future business, and their skills in ICT could allow them to open computer shops or accept sidelines in making invitations, brochures, or catalogs. Based on the narratives, ALS learners were able to pursue their education despite life challenges. Their experiences showed that they never lived smoothly, but life presented them with obstacles that shaped their growth. This study concludes that participation in the ALS program significantly contributed to their personal growth, enabling learners to develop skills, self-motivation, and a sense of purpose as they navigated their educational journey. Definitely, their voices have been heard and showcased in this study for a better understanding of what they have gone through

Recommendations

The study's conclusion led to some recommendations for further research and action:

1. Additional life skills other than weaving Bayong should be taught to the ALS learners for extra income, which would ease a little of the financial crisis they were facing.
2. The ALS program should be promoted, especially in remote areas, so that it is more accessible to all in a conducive learning environment.
3. The ALS program should be given an educational grant or cash for work program to address their financial difficulties.
4. Learners should undergo seminars, trainings, or symposiums that would promote personal growth and skills.
5. Further research could additionally provide in-depth analysis regarding the voices of ALS learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study used the ALS learning environment as an appropriate setting for conducting interviews. Participants' confidentiality and privacy were strictly protected to foster open and honest communication. The researcher obtained informed consent from all ALS learners before allowing them to take part in the study and ensured that participation was entirely voluntary, with the freedom to withdraw at any time without any consequences. All data collected were safely stored and anonymized to preserve

participants' identities. The researcher adhered to ethical standards throughout the study, safeguarding the rights, welfare, and well-being of the learners. Additionally, the study was conducted without bias, and the results were interpreted and reported objectively for research purposes only.

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